

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROBLEMS OF THE RIGHT OF SELF-GOVERNMENT IN
UZBEKISTAN.

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Key words: Right to self-governance, Organization of self-governance organization, basics of self-governance activities, territorial, organizational, financial and economic bases, operation of self-governance organizations, guarantee of self-governance, Nature of guidelines, management powers.

Abstract: In this article considers the development of the problems of the right to self-government in Uzbekistan is carried out in two directions, including the first direction is related to the theoretical foundation of the new branch, its subject, methodology (method), and the determination of its source, the set of norms of the right to self-government is part of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan that the right to self-government is formed as a branch, the principles, institutions and norms of the right to self-government are components of this system.

The development of the problems of the right to self-government is related to the development of law, legislation, and legal science in Uzbekistan to a certain extent.

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The first direction is related to the theoretical foundation of the new network, its subject, methodology (method), and its source. So far, research materials on this problem have been published, monographs and dissertations have appeared. But even though research is still in its infancy, each[2:69] new work is moving toward defining the status of the self-government network.

Legal norms that strengthen and regulate social relations that arise in the process of organizing self-governing organizations and their activities are called self-governing right norms.

The complex of norms of the right to self-government creates the right to self-government as a branch of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan [9:128-131]. The principles, institutions and norms of the right to self-government are components of this system.

Usually, legal norms arise as a result of law-making activities of the state and its organizations. The rules of conduct, which are stated in the normative documents of self-management organizations that are not included in the system of state authorities [3:73] and are binding on everyone, make up a large part of the norms of the right to self-management. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Self-Governing Organizations of Citizens"[1] strengthens the right of self-governing organizations and their officials to make decisions on matters under their control (Article 16).

The characteristic of the norms forming the right to self-governance is that [4:1492-1495], the right to self-governance is at the same time a complex branch of law that includes the norms of the main branches of law, such as Constitutional (state) law, civil law, financial law, etc.

In order to understand the characteristics of the norms of the right to self-government, it is necessary to classify them as follows:

✓ legal norms on the object of legal regulation, that is, on the rule of regulated relations:

- ✓ self-management in the system of public power (concept, principles, functions of self-management);
- ✓ the basics of self-management activities (local, organizational, financial and economic basics);
- ✓ operation of self-management organizations and the subjects of their powers, guarantee of self-management;
- ✓ is divided into provisions that strengthen the responsibility of self-management organizations and their officials.
- ✓ According to the nature of the guidelines, they are:
- ✓ management powers (norms, which determine what self-governing organizations should do, for example, permits that determine work in this field);
- ✓ to binding norms (guidelines on what to do);
- ✓ is divided into prohibition norms (prohibition norms that determine what should not be done).

The last two norms can be explained as follows: self-governing organizations, their [5:135-138] officials are accountable to the population, listen to the reports of the heads of district, city and regional hokims on issues within the sphere of activity of self-governing organizations [6:1-6] is necessary. In these norms, which are called binding, the obligations of the state towards the self-governing organizations and the obligations of the subjects of the right of self-governing are defined [7:121-123]. Norms restricting the right to self-governance, prohibiting interference in the activities of self-governing organizations are prohibitive norms.

In the right to self-government, the provisions announced in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan [15:29] and expressed in the Law "On Self-Governing Organizations of Citizens" can be singled out:

- Self-governing organizations are established in towns, villages, villages, as well as in neighborhoods of cities and districts throughout the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Article 105). Self-governing organizations determine their status and the status of their organizations independently (Articles 8, 11, 12, 13, 14);

- reporting and responsibility of self-governing organizations and officials to the population (Article 29);

- citizens and legal entities (officials of institutions located in the relevant territory) must fulfill the decisions of the self-governing organizations within their powers; Non-implementation of decisions of self-governing organizations of citizens [13:26] and their officials or their decisions cannot be annulled by state organizations [14:69] and officials, these decisions can be declared invalid only by a court decision (19- substance).

Legal institutions included in the network of the right of self-government consist of a group of norms that regulate social relations of a kind related to various aspects of self-government [10:396-400]. Institutions of the right to self-government include: territorial bases of self-government; self-governing organizations and their officials [11:73-76]; issues of local importance and powers of self-government organizations, elections of self-government organizations [11:26-28] and local referendum, property of self-government organizations and so on.

Thus, the legal institution in the right of self-government consists of a set of legal norms that regulate a certain range of interrelated social relations and form a separate, independent group within the subject of the right of self-government.

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